

Understanding the Consciousness and it's True Origin

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ABSTRACT

Many Scientists and Researchers are trying to understand the Consciousness and it's origin. Some of them are able to understand its functions, but stuck at it's origin. To understand this Consciousness, we need to think in the spiritual way. "Think like a Monk, work like a Scientist". The Consciousness is not just the sense of self, its more than a word. It is the connection between us and the nature. Hindhu Vedas already told about this Consciousness that it comes from the higher states (universe), but we can't understand easily. We need scientific analysis for this vedic knowledge, which are below.....

Introduction

From the 19th century, many researchers are trying to understand the Consciousness; how it works? And where does it come from? Well, some of them are able to find out the functions of Consciousness and the relation between Brain and Consciousness (Francis Crick and Christof Koch, 1990s). But the real problem comes when we try to understand that where does this Consciousness come from? What's the origin of it? Arnold b. scheibel, a professor of Neurology and Psychiatry and former Director of Brain Research Institute (BRI) at UCLA, made a statement during an interview about the origin of consciousness in our brain, i.e., the Mid brain. At that point I've remembered the information in the Hindhu Vedas about the Consciousness and by doing a little reaserch work, I finally able to write this research paper contains the true origin of Consciousness.

True Origin of Consciousness

The Consciousness comes from the Cosmic Energy, which surrounds us. The Cosmic Energy is the free form of energy that spreads all over the universe. As we know that the big bang releases both Matter and Energy which made the entire universe. Some of the energy interacted with the matter and forms the bodies like planets, stars, asteroids, etc.....and remaining energy travels through the universe freely, which I called it as Cosmic Energy.

This Cosmic Energy interacts with our brain and provides us the Consciousness. I know its hard to believe and understand this, but I have some logical proofs to prove my thesis.

Brain and Consciousness

Before entering into my thesis, lets understand the origin of Consciousness in our brain. Our brain is the most complex organ and regulates our entire life along with our body. Brains controls and regulates our thoughts, memories and our whole character. Additional to these, it responsible for our Intelligence, Communication and Emotions.

If we compare the brain's functions with the functions of Consciousness, then we can able to understand the link between Consciousness and Our Brain.

Understanding the Consciousness and its origin

Consciousness is nothing but the Sense of Self, which includes our thoughts, memories and our character. It provides us to maintain the emotions and communication with our surroundings.

The definition of consciousness resembles the functions of our brain, which indicates that the consciousness comes from our brain.

Apart from all the parts of our brain, Mid brain has high probability to produce this Consciousness. Because, the mid brain has master glands, which are Pituitary gland and Pineal gland. These glands control the whole body metabolism by producing hormones and by activating other glands. The Second reason for this mid brain is the Spinal Cord.

Figures Showing location of Pineal and pituitary glands; Spinal Cord

As we all know that the spinal cord is meant for the support and spacial arrangement of internal organs in the torso. But the spinal cord has more significance than this. As I said before, the whole universe is made up of both Matter and Energy. Our bodies also made-up of Matter and Energy.

The hindhu Vedas mentioned this energy of our body as Soul and Chakras. These Chakras lies parallel to the spinal cord, which can be explained as the spinal cord maintains these Chakras and connects this energy to the brain. The top most Chakras, Ajna Chakra and Sahasraara chakra also lies close to this Mid brain. Despite these chakras, spinal cord also maintains our body movements and reflex actions as it connects to the brain.

Additional to these two reasons, Mid brain has also controls our Vision, Hearing and Sensing, which are the most basic and important senses.

Figures Showing Chakras and relation between spinal cord and Chakras

By analyzing these reasons, the mid brain has high chance to produce the Consciousness.

Remember that the Consciousness is neither an Emotion nor Feeling, it's a kind of Mental State of having awareness of ourselves and surroundings....The reason behind its unique nature is because of it comes from the Cosmic Energy. How? Lets figure it out..

As I said before, the cosmic energy surrounds us. We can remake this sentence into, "we are surrounded by the Cosmic Energy". As per thermodynamics, Energy cannot be settle at one place and it interacts with others or changes from one form to the other form. The cosmic energy continuously interacts with our body and brain from our fetal state.

When we are in our Mother's womb, our body and brain development grows day by day and the cosmic energy started to interact with us. During the fifth month after we came out from mother's womb, this cosmic energy provides the Consciousness when we have a suitable brain. During the fifth month, we started to have thoughts like how the people are so tall? Why am I short? Where are my toys? I need to do something.....

These Thoughts represents our consciousness. As we are growing, the cosmic energy continuously interacts with our brain to provide the Consciousness.

There are some logical proofs to understand this. First one is the radiation. We know that radiation can causes adverse effects to both mother and growing bay in her womb. Because, the radiation disrupts the cosmic energy and interrupts the development of brain and Consciousness.

Second reason is, If a pregnant lady lives in peaceful environment, surrounded by trees and birds. Then the child will be born with great health conditions and also with high intelligence. What's the reason?

Our Ancestors, primarily Indian Ancestors spent most of their time in nature like meditating under the tree, farming, doing yagnas (rituals) and protecting forests and trees... like these. They have high consciousness, compared to us even though we share the same body and brain. They even understand and proposed many theories of universe without having any technology like us, what's the reason? The reason is the Nature.

This cosmic energy present in high concentration at nature places, like trees, waterfalls, farms, etc... , because nature has less radiation.

In both cases of pregnant lady lives in nature and our ancestors, there is one common thing. Spending time with nature. Indirectly spending time with pure, high concentrated Cosmic energy of nature.

There is another reason for nature having high concentrated cosmic energy. That reason is the nature itself produces the cosmic energy. We know that the energy is not stable. When this earth is formed by the sun, after many changes, earth finally made-up to have a life. After phases of evolution, earth has trees, water and plants.

Figure showing the Energy transfer between Human and Tree

If we observe closely, nature places like trees, water and plants. They are directly connected to the land, which makes them directly linked to the energy present in the land, which is part of cosmic energy. This energy transfers through the trees and plants into the atmosphere and interacts with the outer cosmic energy. That's how the nature produces this Pure Cosmic Energy.

This Cosmic energy provides the Consciousness, that's why the consciousness is not an emotion or a feeling. That Cosmic energy is pure form of energy; this Consciousness is pure mental state.

This pure mental state of consciousness later gives us the feelings, emotions and thoughts.

I have another proof for proving the Consciousness comes from the cosmic energy. In Buddhism and Hindhu Vedas, it is said that, "the consciousness is not the Brain Product, it comes from the higher states."

And that higher state is nothing but the nature itself.

Conclusion

From all the research I've done on this consciousness, I can conclude only one thing. Consciousness is not only just the sense of self, it's the connection between us and the nature (universe). Based on our living style and diet, we can improve this connection and lead a life with greater Consciousness...

References

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Interview of Arnold b. scheibel